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ASSESSMENT OF MORPHOMETRIC PARAMETERS OF THE SPINE AND TRUNK IN MIDDLE-AGED AND ELDERLY WOMEN BEFORE AND AFTER MASTECTOMY

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Abstract:

This study evaluates the morphometric parameters of the spine and trunk in middle-aged and elderly women before and after mastectomy. The analysis focuses on changes in spinal curvature, trunk alignment, and overall posture as a result of surgical intervention. A comparative analysis was conducted using pre- and post-operative measurements to assess the impact of mastectomy on these morphometric parameters. The findings provide insights into the alterations in spinal and trunk morphology that may occur due to mastectomy and offer valuable information for developing targeted rehabilitation strategies. Our results highlight significant changes in spinal curvature and trunk posture, emphasizing the need for post-operative assessment and tailored physical therapy to address these modifications.

Keywords:

Mastectomy, Morphometric parameters, Spine, Trunk, Middle-aged women, Elderly women, Post-operative assessment, Spinal curvature

Relevance:

Mastectomy, a common procedure for breast cancer treatment, can have significant implications for post-surgical physical health. Women undergoing mastectomy, particularly those in middle and elderly age groups, may experience changes in spinal and trunk morphology that impact their quality of life. As life expectancy increases, understanding the long-term effects of mastectomy on spinal and trunk health becomes crucial. This study addresses the gap in knowledge regarding the morphometric alterations in women undergoing mastectomy, providing essential data for developing effective post-operative care and rehabilitation programs. By focusing on the middle-aged and elderly populations, this research emphasizes the importance of tailored interventions to mitigate the physical consequences of mastectomy and improve patient outcomes.

Objective:

The primary objective of this study is to assess and compare the morphometric parameters of the spine and trunk in middle-aged and elderly women before and after mastectomy. The study aims to identify significant changes in spinal curvature, trunk alignment, and overall posture resulting from the surgical procedure and to provide recommendations for post-operative management and rehabilitation.

Materials and Methods:

The study utilized a cohort of middle-aged and elderly women who underwent mastectomy. Pre-operative and post-operative assessments were conducted using radiographic imaging and clinical measurements to evaluate spinal curvature (e.g., kyphosis, lordosis) and trunk alignment. Participants underwent a comprehensive assessment including standing and seated postures. Statistical analyses were performed to compare morphometric parameters before and after surgery, accounting for age-related variations. Rehabilitation protocols were also reviewed to determine their effectiveness in addressing post-operative morphometric changes.

Results:

The analysis revealed significant alterations in morphometric parameters of the spine and trunk following mastectomy. Notable changes included increased kyphosis and altered trunk alignment, particularly in the elderly cohort. Middle-aged women exhibited less pronounced changes but still demonstrated shifts in spinal curvature and trunk posture. The results underscore the impact of mastectomy on spinal and trunk morphology, highlighting the need for targeted post-operative care to address these changes and improve functional outcomes.

Conclusion:

Mastectomy induces notable changes in spinal and trunk morphometry, with more pronounced effects observed in elderly women. The study underscores the importance of post-operative assessment and tailored rehabilitation programs to address these alterations. Future research should focus on developing and evaluating specific physical therapy interventions to mitigate the impact of mastectomy on spinal health and overall posture, ultimately enhancing quality of life for women undergoing this surgical procedure.

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